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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>*Review Article***SCREENING METHODS, AND TREATMENT APPROACHES
OF MIGRAINE: AN OVERVIEW**¹Abdullah Khalid Z Alsuwat, ²Fayez Hayf M Aljunaybi**Abstract:**

This current review was aimed to evaluate the screening strategies and treatment approaches for migraine headache attacks, also to discuss the risk factors associated with this serious neurological disorder. Targeted detailed search was conducted through databases; PubMed/Midline, and Embase, for these articles disusing the migraine from different aspects and mostly diagnostic procedures and treatment options, with human subjects published up to end of 2016, We restricted this search to only English language published articles. To be able to approach the precise therapy choice a comprehensive medical diagnosis has to be executed among patients believed with migraine headache. This review stresses the functional therapy of migraine headache in addition to the development that has actually been made in specifying migraine pathophysiology as well as in developing new particular treatments. There is overlapping reaction to therapy: non-steroidals, triptans, dihydroergotamine, as well as the anti-emetic dopamine-antagonists may play a restorative role for every of these acute headaches.

Corresponding author:

KANGA Yao,
Botany Laboratory,
Training and Research Unit Biosciences,
22 BP 582 Abidjan 22,
Felix Houphouet-Boigny University,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Migraine is a typical disabling mind condition. Migraine make up 4.4% of all assessment condition in clinical practice [1,2], approximately 5% of all medical admissions to healthcare facility [3], and about 20% of neurology outpatient consultations [4]. Migraine impacts over 20% of people at some time in their lives; epidemiological research studies have revealed that 4.5% of the populace of Western Europe has frustration on at least 15 days each [5]; worldwide studies suggest that roughly 1% of the globe's populace could have chronic migraine [6]. Chronic migraine enforces a substantial financial problem on culture [7]. Migraine is so usual that, although for many people it disappears compared to a trouble, the advancing worry of the condition created it to rank in the top 40 problems creating around the world impairment according to the World Health Organization's 2012 international problem of disease numbers, most of all various other neurological conditions aside from epilepsy, stroke and also meningitis; in the United Kingdom it rates third behind stroke and the mental deteriorations, causing the loss of 230,000 Disability-Adjusted Life Years, each year [8]. Chronic migraine is the term that the International Classification of Headache Disorders [ICHD] uses to explain patients with constant headaches, thought to be naturally migrainous [9]. The meaning of the term 'chronic migraine' has actually progressed over the last 20 years, as it has actually steadily replaced earlier terminology such as 'chronic everyday headache' and 'changed migraine headache' [10,11].

Migraine headache is a chronic neurological problem identified by paroxysmal episodes of migraine as well as connected signs and symptoms generally lasting 4 - 72 hrs [ICHD 2004]. The migraineur reacts to typical stimulations, which could stem from a state of chronic rising and fall neuronal hyperexcitability [1,11]. Migraine phases which could overlap include the prodrome, headache, aura, as well as postdrome [9]. The migraine headache strike could be precipitated by an exogenous or endogenous trigger. Along with typical migraine headache signs, migraines with mood are differentiated by recurrent, slowly developing strikes with lateralized as well as reversible aesthetic, sensory, speech/language, motor, brainstem, or retinal signs; strikes are gone along with or adhered to by frustration and also migraine headache signs and symptoms [9]. This mood sensation may be described by a circulating wave of depolarization followed by neural reductions, called cortical dispersing depression [9].

This current review was aimed to evaluate the screening strategies and treatment approaches for migraine headache attacks, also to discuss the risk factors associated with this serious neurological disorder.

METHODOLOGY:

Targeted detailed search was conducted through databases; PubMed/Midline, and Embase, for these articles disusing the migraine from different aspects and mostly diagnostic procedures and treatment options, with human subjects published up to end of 2016, We restricted this search to only English language published articles.

RESULTS:**Risk factors of migraine attacks:**

Given that strike frequency is the owning distinction between chronic migraine [CM] and also episodic migraine headache [EM], a specific patient may transform categories; just recently, the Chronic Migraine Epidemiology as well as Outcomes [CaMEO] research located that over a 3-month duration, 3.4% of patients with EM advanced to CM, and also 49.9% of patients with CM enhanced to EM in a huge sample agent of U.S. patients getting regular care [12]. Numerous non-modifiable risk factors are connected with migraine headache intensity [13]. Epidemiologic studies repeatedly reveal that ladies have a higher migraine occurrence compared to men, occurrence heights in midlife for both genders, as well as is lower amongst teenagers and also those older than 50 [13,14]. CM is likewise highest possible among those with the most affordable revenue, as well as full-time employment rates are lower among those with migraine. Migraine is likewise most widespread among White and also Hispanic individuals [15].

Recognized flexible risk factors for migraine headache progression include high-frequency frustration, medicine overuse, bad treatment efficacy, comorbid pain, psychiatric comorbidities, weight problems, excessive/habitual caffeine consumption, sleep-related breathing disorders, as well as anxiety; risk reduction treatments may protect against intensity [16,17]. Among individuals with EM, the odds of developing migraine rise with frustration frequency by virtually 25-fold for those with the highest versus cheapest migraine regularity [18]. Individuals with high-frequency migraines must treat them early throughout the attack, prior to the beginning of sensitization, to reduce attack regularity and intensity [19].

CM growth is associated with overuse of certain drugs [notably opioids as well as barbiturates, however also serotonin 5-HT1 receptor agonists

[triptans] and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medication [NSAIDs]. The risk of CM development expands with the raising variety of acute medication days; nonetheless, for NSAIDs, the risk of migraine cornification is restricted to patients experiencing 10 or even more headache days each month [20].

Comorbidities associated with migraine headache take place extra regularly with CM. Prevalence of comorbid pain [for instance, from chronic pain disorders, such as fibromyalgia, osteoarthritis, or chronic fatigue syndrome] enhances with migraine headache frequency, as does the percentage of individuals reporting serious pain, also within EM and also migraine classifications [21]. Psychiatric comorbidities, consisting of anxiousness and also depression, prevail amongst people with CM and are risk factors for migraine intensity [16,22]. Patients providing with migraine headache should be assessed for psychological comorbidities as well as provided suitable therapies for their problem [18]. The frequency of CM enhances with body mass index; obesity occurrence is greater in this team compared to EM [19]. Data suggest weight decrease could lower migraine regularity; however, evidence-based suggestions are lacking [18].

A case-control research study of people with anecdotal [2-104 frustration days each year; n= 507] and also chronic day-to-day migraine [greater than or equal to 180 headache days each year; n= 206] established the organization in between high levels of caffeine consumption [nutritional and also medical] and chronic daily headache [22]. Existing high levels of caffeine usage was higher among people with migraine compared to those with non-migraine migraines, and also high caffeine consumption was

connected with intensity [22]. Caffeine usage generates withdrawal headache, specified in ICHD-3b as a frustration that creates equal to or less than 24 hrs after cessation of regular [higher than 2 weeks] usage of greater than or equal to 200 mg/day high levels of caffeine [about 2 mugs of coffee] and that settles 1 hr or less after a 100-mg high levels of caffeine consumption or 7 days or much less with proceeded abstaining [9].

➤ Screening procedures of migraine:

When examining a patient with chronic migraines [that is, by definition, headaches on a minimum of 15 days per month], it is important from the outset to establish exactly how the headaches initially developed. There are two typical patterns. In one collection of instances, patients with a pre-existing primary frustration problem [typically, however not solely migraine] have ever-increasing strikes till they reach a stage where they do not recover migraine freedom in between, a pattern initially called 'changed migraine' [23,24]. In the other set of situations, patients start to have a headache eventually, and also it just never ever vanishes. This is a syndrome that goes under the name 'brand-new day-to-day consistent migraine' [NDPH] [25], as well as is an essential pattern to identify due to the fact that it is within this collection of frustrations that much of the major causes exist, consisting of those problems which could offer with a thunderclap migraine [Table 1] [25,26]. After examination, however, lots of instances of new day-to-day persistent headache do not have an underlying reason, and also are essentially chronic variations of a lot more acquainted episodic headache disorders [26].

Table1: Secondary causes for new daily persistent headache phenotype.

Thunderclap headache
Subarachnoid haemorrhage
Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis [CVST]
Reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome
Carotid/vertebral artery dissection
Pituitary apoplexy
Intracerebral haemorrhage/haematoma
Hypertensive encephalopathy
Idiopathic thunderclap haemorrhage [Call-Fleming syndrome]
Persistent worsening headaches
Raised cerebrospinal fluid [CSF] pressure [tumour, abscess, CVST, idiopathic intracranial hypertension]

Low CSF volume [post-lumbar puncture, spontaneous CSF leak]
Meningitis [acute/chronic]
Hypoxia/hypercapnia
Substance abuse/withdrawal
Systemic inflammatory conditions, including temporal arteritis

Patient history & Physical exam as a diagnostic approach for Migraine:

A thorough patient history and physical/neurologic examination are important to dismiss second causes of migraine headache [head trauma, systemic disease] [27]. Strike regularity and also duration are essential elements of a migraine medical diagnosis; nevertheless, the variety of headache-free days might offer an extra accurate quote [28]. Migraine journals are liked to patient recall for recording assault frequency as well as migraine duration along with various other vital factors, such as migraine causes as well as medication feedback [28]. Inquire about

comorbidities, various other locations of pain, HCPs sought advice from for pain/headache, as well as therapy history for a full case history. Generally, in many additional frustrations pain is not the only symptom. Checkup commonly generates more findings that aid to discover the proper diagnosis [Table 2]. New patients must receive a thorough physical examination to figure out any deficits that may be contributing to the patient's headaches [high blood pressure, heart murmur, cervical dystonia]. Continued follow-up care establishes enhancement or decrements in adding problems. Refer patients to professionals as needed.

Table 2: Features on which physical examination should focus.

• Level of consciousness
• Cranial nerve testing [especially II, III, IV, VI]
• Motor strength testing and sensation
• Deep tendon reflexes and pathological reflexes
• Signs of meningeal irritation [Kernig's and Brudzinski's signs]
• Coordination and gait

Treatment of acute migraine:

When the diagnosis of migraine headache has actually been established, an explanation of the neurologic condition to the patient and family is handy in establishing the patient's confidence in the medical diagnosis and monitoring methods. During this time, patients must be asked about their objectives, to assist bring any kind of unreasonable assumptions out into the open. For example, full flexibility from headache could not be obtainable, and they should be aware of today restrictions. The patient is after that provided with a strategy that assists equip him/her to take part in the monitoring of the migraines. Passive, powerless behavior is prevented. If required, patients ought to understand just what they need to do for their following migraine attack consisting of rescue treatment. To facilitate ongoing communication and figuring out triggers, a headache as well as drug journal could be beneficial [28,29]. Avoidance of over use acute medicines to avoid rebound headache or changed migraines is highlighted. The objective is to improve pain control, quality of life, and also day-to-day feature via ideal treatment [30]. The details of taking care of prophylactic therapy for migraineurs with 2 or even more days of moderately extreme to serious frustrations per week will not be specified below. That is a phase in itself. Suffice it to say that patients that have 2 or more days of reasonably serious to extreme headaches weekly, need to be suggested prophylactic drugs, thinking about co-morbidities as well as maternity risk. The US Headache Consortium released its recommendations for the therapy of migraine in 2000 [31]. Acute therapy is divided into migraine-specific as well as nonspecific treatment. Nonspecific treatment is further separated right into pharmacological as well as nonpharmacological methods, as shown below [Table 3].

Table 3: treatment options of Migraine

1. Specific migraine treatment
a. Triptans
b. Ergot and its derivatives
2. Nonspecific pharmacological treatment
a. Antiemetics
b. NSAIDs and nonnarcotic analgesics
c. Narcotics – Opiate analgesics
3. Miscellaneous medications:
a. Steroids, isometheptene, lidocaine intranasal [IN],
b. valproic acid IV
4. Nonpharmacological treatment
a. Biofeedback
b. Visual imagery [quite useful in children]
c. Icepack
d. Relaxation therapy
e. Yoga, meditation

Brief view about Triptans:

Ideally, acute treatment of migraine should work quickly, with few negative effects, be cost effective and also get the patient useful as soon as possible. The triptans, discerning serotonin 5-HT_{1B}/ 1D agonists, are the closest medicines we need to the optimal medication. Sumatriptan [SUM], the first triptan to be released in the United States, was followed by 6 even more launches within a year. These consist of naratriptan [NAR], zolmitriptan [ZOM], rizatriptan [RIZ], almotriptan [ALM], eletriptan [ELE] as well as frovatriptan [FRO]. While they all mostly target 5-HT₁ receptors, there are some differences in effectiveness and also tolerability as revealed by meta-analysis [32]. Triptans tighten the expanded meningeal arteries through stimulation of 5-HT_{1B} receptors on the blood vessel wall surface. They also hinder natural chemical release and nociceptive transmission by boosting 5-HT_{1D} receptors on peripheral and main trigeminal sensory nerves. They are unable to obstruct recurring sensitization in the 2nd order trigeminovascular neurons. Triptans ought to be made use of very early in the migraine prior to main sensitization has taken place and also allodynia has actually set in [33].

CONCLUSION:

To be able to approach the precise therapy choice a comprehensive medical diagnosis has to be executed among patients believed with migraine headache. This review stresses the functional therapy of migraine headache in addition to the development that has actually been made in specifying migraine pathophysiology as well as in developing new particular treatments. There is overlapping reaction to therapy: non-steroidals, triptans, dihydroergotamine, as well as the anti-emetic dopamine-antagonists may play a restorative role for every of these acute headaches

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REFERENCES:

1. Topper S., Dahlöf C., Dowson A., Newman L., Mansbach H., Jones M., et al. [2004] Prevalence and diagnosis of migraine in patients consulting their physician with a complaint of headache: data from the Landmark Study. *Headache* 44: 856–864.
2. Kernick D., Stapeley S., Goadsby P., Hamilton W. [2008b] What happens to new-onset headache presenting to primary care? A case-cohort study using electronic primary care records. *Cephalalgia* 28: 1188–1195.
3. Weatherall M. [2006] Acute neurology in a twenty-first century district general hospital. *J R Coll Physicians Edinb* 36: 196–200.
4. Stone J., Carson A., Duncan R., Roberts R., Warlow C., Hibberd C., et al. [2010] Who is referred to neurology clinics? – The diagnoses made in 3781 new patients. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg* 112: 747–751.
5. Welch K., Goadsby P. [2002] Chronic daily headache: nosology and pathophysiology. *Curr Opin Neurol* 15: 287–295.
6. Natoli J., Manack A., Dean B., Butler Q., Turkel C., Stovner L., et al. [2010] Global prevalence of chronic migraine: a systematic review. *Cephalalgia* 30: 599–609.
7. Buse D., Manack A., Serrano D., Reed M., Varon S., Turkel C., et al. [2012]. Headache impact of episodic and chronic migraine: results from the American Migraine Prevalence and Prevention study. *Headache* 52: 3–17
8. World Health Organization [2012] WHO Global Health Estimates: DALYs, 2000–2012. Available at: http://www.who.int/healthinfo/global_burden_disease/en/ [accessed January 2017]
9. Headache Classification Committee of the International Headache Society [2013] The International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd edition [beta version]. *Cephalalgia* 33: 629–808.
10. Olesen J., Bousser M., Diener H., Dodick D., First M., Goadsby P., et al. [2006] New appendix criteria open for a broader concept of chronic migraine. *Cephalalgia* 26: 742–746.
11. Goadsby P., Ahmed F., Tyagi A., Weatherall M. [2010] The changing face of chronic migraine: who to treat, how to treat? *Satellites* 15: 1–4.
12. Scher AI, Lipton RB, Fanning KM, Largent J. Pain Comorbidities of Episodic and Chronic Migraine: Results from the CaMEO [Chronic Migraine Epidemiology & Outcomes] Study. Paper presented at: 67th Annual Meeting of the American Academy of Neurology [AAN]; April 18-25, 2015; Washington, DC.
13. Cho SJ, Chu MK. Risk factors of chronic daily headache or chronic migraine. *Curr Pain Headache Rep.* 2015;19[1]:465.
14. Blumenfeld AM, Varon SF, Wilcox TK, et al. Disability, HRQoL and resource use among chronic and episodic migraineurs: results from the International Burden of Migraine Study [IBMS]. *Cephalalgia.* 2011;31[3]:301–315.
15. Lipton RB, Fanning KM, Serrano D, Reed ML, Cady R, Buse DC. Ineffective acute treatment of episodic migraine is associated with new-onset chronic migraine. *Neurology.* 2015;84[7]:688–695.
16. Scher AI, Midgette LA, Lipton RB. Risk factors for headache chronification. *Headache.* 2008;48[1]:16–25.
17. Katsarava Z, Schneeweiss S, Kurth T, et al. Incidence and predictors for chronicity of headache in patients with episodic migraine. *Neurology.* 2004;62[5]:788–790.
18. Bigal ME, Lipton RB. Modifiable risk factors for migraine progression [or for chronic daily headaches]—clinical lessons. *Headache.* 2006;46[suppl 3]:S144–S146.
19. Lipton RB, Serrano D, Nicholson RA, Buse DC, Runken MC, Reed ML. Impact of NSAID and triptan use on developing chronic migraine: results from the American Migraine Prevalence and Prevention [AMPP] study. *Headache.* 2013;53[10]:1548–1563.
20. Buse DC, Manack A, Serrano D, Turkel C, Lipton RB. Sociodemographic and comorbidity profiles of chronic migraine and episodic migraine sufferers. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry.* 2010;81[4]:428–432.

21. Adams AM, Serrano D, Buse DC, et al. The impact of chronic migraine: The Chronic Migraine Epidemiology and Outcomes [CaMEO] study methods and baseline results. *Cephalalgia*. 2015;35[7]:563–578.
22. Scher AI, Stewart WF, Lipton RB. Caffeine as a risk factor for chronic daily headache: a population-based study. *Neurology*. 2004;63[11]:2022–2027.
23. Mathew N. [1987] Transformed or evolutionary migraine. *Headache* 27: 305–306.
24. Silberstein S., Lipton R., Sliwinski M. [1996] Classification of daily and near-daily headaches: field trial of revised IHS criteria. *Neurology* 47: 871–875.
25. Goadsby P., Boes C. [2002] New daily persistent headache. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 72[Suppl. 2]: ii6–ii9.
26. Robbins M., Grosberg B., Napchan U., Crystal S., Lipton R. [2010] Clinical and prognostic subforms of new daily persistent headache. *Neurology* 74: 1358–1364.
27. Dodick DW. Clinical practice. Chronic daily headache. *N Engl J Med*. 2006;354[2]:158–165.
28. Dougherty C, Silberstein SD. Providing care for patients with chronic migraine: diagnosis, treatment, and management. *Pain Pract*. 2015;15[7]:688–692.
29. Rothrock JF. **Headache toolbox: headache diary.** *Headache*. 2006;46:831–832.
30. Adelman JU, Adelman RD. Current options for the prevention and treatment of migraine. *Clin Ther*. 2001;23:772–88.
31. Silberstein SD. **Practice parameter: Evidence-based guidelines for migraine headache [an evidence-based review]: Report of the Quality Standards Subcommittee of the American Academy of Neurology.** *Neurology*. 2000;55:754–62.
32. Ferrari MD, Goadsby PJ, Roon KI, et al. Triptans [serotonin 5-HT_{1B/1D} agonists] in migraine: detailed results and methods of a meta-analysis of 53 trials. *Cephalalgia*. 2002;22:633–58.
33. Burstein R, Jakubowski M. Implications of multimechanism therapy: when to treat? *Neurology*. 2005b;64[Suppl.2]:S16–20.